

Jehovah's Witnesses

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The religious movement that would grow into the Jehovah's Witnesses first coalesced in Pittsburgh in the 1870s around a young founder named Charles Taze Russell. Though previously disillusioned with religion, Russell was strongly influenced by Adventist ideas of Jesus' imminent return. He began gathering friends and followers at a Bible Study and publishing a periodical called "Zion's Watch Tower and Herald of Christ's Presence." By the 1880s, Russell's congregations had proliferated, and he had formally founded the organization that would become the Watch Tower Bible and Tract Society, the guiding institution behind the Jehovah's Witnesses. But the Jehovah's Witnesses faced a prophetic challenge as a mounting number of revised dates that Russell continued to set for the apocalypse came and went without Christ's tangible return. After another apparently failed prophecy in 1914, Witnesses began to argue that Jesus had indeed returned, but had done so invisibly, beginning a heavenly rule and ushering in the "last days" that will lead up to an imminent Battle of Armageddon. Soon, they believe, Jesus will purge the earth of sin and wickedness, creating a paradise. A small group of elite believers will rule over it with him, while the rest of the righteous will be reawakened to live eternally on the new earth. Nonbelievers will be punished with eternal death. Because of their belief that the Apocalypse is imminent, Witnesses are hyper focused on proselytizing in their home communities and around the world. They do this through door-to-door outreach and by distributing literature in public places like train and subway stations. Through a tight organizational structure led by the Governing Body at a global level and elders at a congregational level, Jehovah's Witness' variations in practice, belief, and biblical interpretation are kept in check. Beyond their outreach efforts, Jehovah's Witnesses are fairly insular, maintaining strong boundaries between insiders and outsiders. They are a relatively "high cost" religious group in terms of the demands they place on members' time, energy, and autonomy. They also stand out from other Christian groups for their rejection of the trinity, as well as for their refusal to celebrate holidays, participate in politics or shows of patriotism, or receive blood transfusions. Over the last century, Jehovah's Witnesses have often faced intense persecution around the globe.

Date Range: 1870 CE - 2022 CE

Region: World-wide

Region tags: Global

Jehovah's Witnesses originated in the United States, but have long emphasized worldwide missions and have congregations in almost every nation. Globally, their congregations have a strikingly consistent pattern of beliefs, rituals, and institutional structures. The map highlights places that have organizational significance to the group: Pittsburgh, where the Jehovah's Witnesses were founded; Brooklyn, NY, where their worldwide headquarters were housed for over a century; and Warwick, NY, where they are now headquartered.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Andrew Holden, *Jehovah's Witnesses: Portrait of a Contemporary Religious Movement*. (Florence: Taylor & Francis Group, 2002.)
- Source 2: M. James Penton, *Apocalypse Delayed: the Story of Jehovah's Witnesses*. (Toronto: University of Toronto Press, 1985.)
- Source 3: Weddle, David L., "A New 'Generation' of Jehovah's Witnesses: Revised Interpretation, Ritual, and Identity." *Nova Religio: The Journal of Alternative and Emergent Religions* 3, no. 2 (2000): 350–67.

Notes: There has been surprisingly little scholarly work written about Jehovah's Witnesses, though these three sources are insightful examples. Most of the literature that exists about the group is either theological (Christian literature contesting the group's religious claims) or activist/investigative (often anti-cult literature focused on exposing what is described as a manipulative, abusive, and dangerous group). Much of the latter is written by ex-Witnesses.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: Douglas Quenqua, "A Secret Database of Child Abuse," *The Atlantic*, March 22, 2019.
- Source 1 Description: In investigating sexual abuse within the religious movement, this lengthy Atlantic story describes Witnesses' insular and intensely patriarchal culture.
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.amazon.com/The-Witnesses-Season-1/dp/B084TDMXC8>
- Source 2 Description: This two-part documentary released in 2020 chronicles extensive coverups of child sexual abuse within the Jehovah's Witnesses.
- Source 3 URL: https://www.vicetv.com/en_us/video/crusaders/60f82b9a4da46408cb4b3063
- Source 3 Description: This Vice documentary released in 2021 offers further investigation into the sexual abuse scandals that have surrounded Jehovah's Witnesses.

Notes: As these sources show, many of the sources online about Jehovah's Witnesses are coming at the religious group through an investigative angle, and many of them focus on recent sexual abuse coverups that have now come to light.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: www.jw.org
- Source 1 Description: This is the Jehovah's Witness' main website, run by the Watch Tower Society. It contains videos, images, and extensive biblical exegesis.
- Source 2 URL: <https://wol.jw.org/>
- Source 2 Description: This is a collection of Watch Tower publications (magazines, pamphlets, workbooks, etc.) dating back several decades. It also includes an online version of the New World Translation of the Bible.
- Source 3 URL: <https://jwwatch.org>
- Source 3 Description: This blog gathers news articles about Witnesses, leaked videos, and other (mostly incendiary) material. It is explicitly aimed at combatting the power of the Governing Body for an audience of mostly ex-Jehovah's Witnesses.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: In most contexts, Jehovah's Witnesses are seeking to draw believers away from other groups, and vis versa.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: "Conflict" is not the right word here, but Jehovah's Witnesses have faced violent repression in some countries around the world, including in Russia and China.
<https://www.state.gov/international-religious-freedom-or-belief-alliance-statement-on-jehovahs-witnesses/>

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

Notes: Although Jehovah's Witnesses believe that children born into Jehovah's Witnesses families are given special consideration from God because of their parents' righteousness (i.e. if they die in childhood, they may be saved), they also believe that teens or adults must choose to be baptized into the church in order to become full members.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Notes: Although age does not automatically trigger membership, Witnesses cannot be baptized until their later teenage years, usually when they are 16 or older.

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: To be acknowledged as a Jehovah's Witness an individual must be baptized in the church.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Proselytizing is an absolute pillar of Jehovah's Witnesses' lives.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: Witnesses don't have religious professionals. All baptized members are considered "publishers," and are responsible for spreading God's word.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

Notes: All Witnesses are expected to serve as "missionaries" in some way, shape, or form. But only some choose to travel to devote themselves to missionary work. Those that do must first be invited to attend the Watchtower Bible School of Gilead, a training school for missionaries.

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Notes: This is a controversial question. Most scholars would argue that Witnesses' proselytization is not coercive, as it involves no force and no threats. Disgruntled ex-members and activists who brand Jehovah's Witnesses as a cult, however, have argued that Witnesses by "love bombing" potential converts or by targeting unhappy people for conversion, they are coercively ensnaring recruits.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: Jehovah's Witnesses have often been regarded with suspicion by state authorities. Typically, this is due to their subversive refusal to participate in anything political, from serving in the military to voting to saluting a state flag. They have also been banned or targeted for outright persecution in a number of countries. For an overview of legal battles over Witnesses' refusal to salute the flag in the U.S.A., see https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0jo6Wwj_ft4.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:

– Yes

Notes: Apostates are disfellowshipped and shunned. They are considered to pose a dangerous threat to the entire religious body of believers.

<https://www.jw.org/en/library/books/Reasoning-From-the-Scriptures/Apostasy/>

↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:

– No

↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:

– No

↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:

– Yes

↳ Punished in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: As former Witness Amber Scolah has described, apostasy is conceptualized as the worst sin for Jehovah's Witnesses, and as the only unforgivable sin. Apostates are therefore guaranteed to be condemned to eternal death. (<https://www.npr.org/transcripts/735352084>).

↳ Cursed by "high god":

– No

↳ Cursed by other supernatural being(s):

– No

↳ Other divine punishment:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 8686980

Notes: This number comes from the Watch Tower Society's 2021 reporting on active, enrolled members of the church: <https://www.jw.org/en/jehovahs-witnesses/faq/how-many-jw/>. Numbers vary widely county to country, with the largest numbers of Witnesses in the US, Mexico, Brazil, and Nigeria.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 0.1

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Jehovah's Witnesses regard the Hebrew Bible and the New Testament as their

scripture. The New World Translation, published by the Watch Tower Society, is their preferred translation, replacing the King James translation they previously used.

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Notes: Jehovah's Witnesses believe the Bible was written by many individual men, but was inspired by Jehovah, the one true god. Although it was inspired, not revealed, they believe it to be infallible.

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: The Bible is understood to be perfectly complete.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: Outside of the Watch Tower headquarters, "Kingdom Halls" are the only buildings Jehovah's Witnesses construct for religious purposes. They are framed as meeting places but quite deliberately not cast as ritually sacred space. Apart from the words "Kingdom Hall" on the outside, the buildings are typically inconspicuous, without steeples, crosses, or other religious iconography. Inside, they often resemble corporate conference spaces, though they may be decorated with Bible verses. For a video on the role of Kingdom Halls from the Jehovah's Witnesses, see <https://www.jw.org/en/jehovahs-witnesses/meetings/video-kingdom-hall/>.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Notes: Witnesses are opposed to iconography. The worship spaces in their Kingdom Halls are free of religious symbols, and Witnesses reject the significance of the cross, believing it to be a historically inaccurate symbol of Jesus' death. However, Witnesses may display paintings or artwork in their homes featuring images of Jesus, the New Kingdom to come, or Bible verses. For examples of this kind of art, see "jwcreativetreasures" on etsy: https://www.etsy.com/shop/jwcreativetreasures?ref=simple-shop-header-name&listing_id=1189853812.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: Spirits have the potential to be eternal. Unlike most Christians, Witnesses do not believe that all humans have immortal souls or spirits. Rather, the souls of unbelievers are understood to truly die with their bodies, while the spirits of believers fall asleep at death and will be re-awaken at the time of Christ's millennial return.

Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: Witnesses are quite clear that bodies are disposable containers for the soul; they are therefore not overly concerned with what happens to the body itself after death.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: As a millenarian movement, the Jehovah's Witnesses are extremely focused on the afterlife. Within their framing, the afterlife does not begin for people individually when they die, but rather will begin for all humanity soon when the Battle of Armageddon takes place and Jesus ushers in God's new kingdom.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Witnesses believe that after Armageddon, God will create a new heaven and a new earth. An elite few believers will be chosen by God to live in his new heaven and to rule alongside Jesus (<https://www.jw.org/en/bible-teachings/questions/go-to-heaven/>). The afterlife for most believers, however, will take place in the perfected, Edenic version of Earth. Until their resurrection, dead Witnesses are understood to be asleep in their graves, not in another realm. For a discussion of how resolutely focused on the material reality of the new earth Witnesses' millennial visions are, see Holden, 94.

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– Yes [specify]: Perfected version of the earth.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Notes: Adherents' bodies are considered to be empty vessels, and are treated respectfully after death but not with religious reverence. Funerals are generally conducted according to the traditions of the adherents' home countries.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: Witnesses are comfortable using local burial practices, as they don't believe that the form of burial impacts God's ability to resurrect believers. See <https://www.jw.org/en/bible-teachings/questions/bible-about-cremation/> for a discussion of acceptable practices.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: Jehovah is the supreme high god, or "Almighty God."

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: Witnesses go further than many Christian groups in conceptualizing God as a "spirit person." In particular, they push back against the notion of God's omnipresence, instead arguing that he lives in a specific heavenly realm. Witnesses believe that God, like all spirits, is genderless, but that because his role as head of all creation aligns with the role of men on earth as heads of households, it is proper to use male pronouns and male imagery around him. (<https://wol.jw.org/en/wol/d/r1/lp-e/102008370>)

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: God is understood to live in the heavenly realm, conceptualized as above the earth.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: For an extensive discussion of the abundance of God's goodness, see

<https://wol.jw.org/en/wol/d/r1/lp-e/1989881?q=god+good&p=doc>.

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: God's true name is Jehovah.

Notes: Witnesses are adamant that God has a personal name, and that name is Jehovah. For more on why they believe this is so theologically important, see <https://www.jw.org/en/library/magazines/watchtower-no1-2019-jan-feb/what-is-gods-name/>

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: God is all-knowing (<https://wol.jw.org/en/wol/d/r1/lp-e/1986361?q=omniscient&p=doc>).

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: Because of this, ritual efficacy is considered to be dependant on intention. Religious practices like prayer and fasting are only efficacious if done with a pure and humble heart.

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: Jehovah's Witnesses emphatically believe in free will over predestination. However, they also believe that God has foreknowledge of everything.

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
– Yes [specify]: Jehovah is all-knowing.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

Notes: Jehovah's Witnesses see God as directly intervening both in the individual lives of humans and in the course of world history. That said, they don't see him as choosing to intervene in petty or worldly ways; ethnographer Andrew Holden describes a Witness brushing aside the idea that Jehovah would intervene to help her and her husband move into a nicer house (Holden, 133).

↳ The supreme high god can reward:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– No

Notes: Jehovah can work through human actors, including but not limited to working through Witnesses. Sending Jesus as an agent of transformation was one way that Jehovah had an enormous but indirect causal effect on the world.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– Yes

Notes: God can be pleased with his people, and can show positive emotions like

delight.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The Jehovah's Witnesses see themselves as following an Old Testament God who also shows anger when his will is not obeyed.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: Witnesses are fairly anxious about the risk of idolatry, even accidental. For this reason they avoid holidays that have any origins in pagan religion.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: God is not a trinity, but a singular being.

Notes: Witnesses stand out among Christians for their rejection of trinitarian theology.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: God has the capacity to offer direct revelation to his prophets, Witnesses believe, and did so to communicate with the ancient Israelites. But they argue that that Jesus' sacrifice marked a historical shift in God's relation to humankind, and that he no longer speaks in such a direct way to his people. But Witnesses stress that he still communicates constantly (with those who choose to listen) through the Bible, through prayer, and through the Watch Tower Society.

↳ In dreams:

– No

Notes: Witnesses believe God has the capacity to communicate through dreams, and there are Biblical examples of this. However, the Watchtower Society argues that even in the Bible this was a very rare occurrence, and urges Witnesses to therefore avoid looking to their dreams for divine communication. (<https://wol.jw.org/en/wol/d/r1/lp-e/102001248>)

↳ In trance possession:

– No

Notes: Witnesses see possession as a dangerous occult practice.

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

Notes: Witnesses are emphatic in the distinction they draw between divination (an occult, sinful practice, even if it yields correct information about the future) and true revelation from God (<https://wol.jw.org/en/wol/d/r1/lp-e/1200001200?q=divination&p=doc>).

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: The Bible, Prayer, the Watch Tower Society.

Notes: To Witnesses, the Bible represents an open line to God. Through it he can communicate timeless truths and all of the guidance humankind needs to cope with the evolving challenges of earthly life. They see prayer as a way for every believer to seek God's counsel and ask for his help. (<https://www.jw.org/en/library/magazines/wp20140401/does-god-answer-prayers/>) They also believe that God has uniquely equipped the Watch Tower Society to interpret the Bible, and to serve as a mouthpiece for God's word. (<https://wol.jw.org/en/wol/d/r1/lp-e/1967081?q=god+speak&p=doc>)

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

Notes: Jehovah's Witnesses believe that the human dead are asleep until Armageddon.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Witnesses believe Jesus to be a divine spirit. However, unlike most Christians, they do not believe that he is a part of a trinity or on equal footing with the high God. Instead, they believe he was Jehovah's first creation, and acts as an instrument of God's will. They also believe in angels, who they cast as spirits who God created and gave the free will to serve him or to rebel against him.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Witnesses believe that both Jesus and God's angels have taken physical form in the past and will do so again in the future, beginning with the Battle of Armageddon.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: Witnesses emphasize Jesus' full, embodied humanity during his time on earth. They also emphasize that angels in the past have come as tangible people, and that now angels may come in many forms or may work

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

Notes: Angels are not considered omniscient (<https://www.jw.org/en/library/magazines/watchtower-no5-2017-september/truth-about-angels/>). Unlike most Christians, Witnesses also do not consider Jesus to be omniscient; according to their reading of the Bible, he had to wait patiently to be told by Jehovah when the Battle of Armageddon was to begin (<https://wol.jw.org/en/wol/d/r1/lp-e/1996567>).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: Jesus can see all humans at all times. There is murkiness within Watch Tower theology surrounding what limits there may be on angels' knowledge and ability to observe human lives; they have greater knowledge and powers than humans, but only Jehovah is thought to be omniscient. This ambiguity is

clear in Witness texts (e.g. <https://www.jw.org/en/library/magazines/watchtower-no5-2017-september/truth-about-angels/>).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: See above.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: This is true for Jesus, who can read the inner thoughts of humankind (<https://www.jw.org/en/library/jw-meeting-workbook/november-2019-mwb/meeting-schedule-november18-24/i-know-your-deeds/>). Ambiguity remains about whether or not angels have access to humans' innermost thoughts.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: See above. As with hidden motives, Witnesses believe that Jesus can see humans' basic character, but are unsure of whether angels may or may not be able to.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: Jesus has almost complete future sight. However, there is a sliver of difference left between the perfect foreknowledge of Jehovah-God (<https://www.jw.org/en/library/magazines/wp20140501/does-god-know-the-future/>) and the lesser foreknowledge of Jesus. The foresight of angels remains ambiguous (<https://www.jw.org/en/library/magazines/watchtower-no5-2017-september/angel-help/>).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: When Armageddon will unfold.

Notes: Witnesses believe that when Jesus walked the earth, he did not know when or how the world would end. However, in 1914 he took his place as king of the new heaven, and that at that time he was given knowledge of the divine timeline for Armageddon.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Both Jesus and angels are tasked with helping to roll out the divine plan. This includes aiding the righteous and punishing or purging the wicked.

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Witnesses believe that God often intercedes not through miracles but in quiet, indirect ways, like by inspiring a friend to reach out and help, or by giving an individual the strength to persevere through a hardship. See the following article on jw.org for a discussion of the "very subtle ways" that God can intervene in believers' lives: <https://www.jw.org/en/library/magazines/wp20140401/does-god-answer-prayers/>.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Both Jesus and the angels are seen as embodying God's will, which includes embodying and enacting both his love and his anger.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: See above.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: Although Witnesses believe in demons, they argue that they are simply angels that

have fallen away from God. (<https://www.jw.org/en/bible-teachings/questions/are-demons-real/>)

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– No

Notes: Many of the sins Jehovah is most concerned with (premarital or extramarital sexual activity, celebrating holidays, accepting blood transfusions) have little to do with the social cohesion of the group. Rather, they concern maintaining a hard boundary between righteous insiders and sinful outsiders.

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– Yes

Notes: The taboo on consuming blood is so important to God that he requires his followers to reject blood transfusions even in life-threatening cases. The Watch Tower's magazine, "Awake!" has addressed this issue extensively, as in this 1985 issue where it urged Witnesses to reject blood transfusions even if they were privately pressured by a doctor to accept them in secret: <https://wol.jw.org/en/wol/d/r1/lp-e/1985283?q=blood+transfusion&p=par#h=20>.

↳ Sacred space(s):

– No

Notes: There is not a strong concept of sacred space for Jehovah's Witnesses.

↳ Sacred object(s):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Masturbation and Premarital Sex

– Yes [specify]: Sexual Abuse

Notes: Over recent decades, Jehovah's Witnesses' handling of sexual abuse cases have come under scrutiny - and in particular, their pattern of handling abuse in-house rather than reporting it to law enforcement. In 2005, Carol J. Adams published an article arguing that although the church classes child abuse as a grave sin, it also sets unreasonably high standards of proof that discourage victims from coming forward. (See Carol J. Adams, *The Response of the Jehovah's Witnesses to Child Sexual Abuse*. *Journal of Religion and Abuse* 7 (4) 2005: pp. 41-54. The article can be accessed in its entirety here: <https://caroljadams.com/carol-adams-blog/a-policy-that-insures-failure>.) In recent new reports, alleged victims of child abuse within the Jehovah's Witnesses have also claimed that when they reported sexual abuse to elders, it was treated as a mutual sexual sin, and they were told they had to seek God's forgiveness and even censured in front of their congregations. For an in-depth examination of this dynamic, see <https://www.theatlantic.com/family/archive/2019/03/the-secret-jehovahs-witness-database-of-child-molesters/584311/>. Surprisingly, this topic has received little scholarly attention. In 2022, Faisal Rashid and Ian Barron published an article in the *Journal of Sexual Aggression* calling for more research into the issue (Faisal Rashid and Ian Barron, *Jehovah's Witnesses Response to Child Sexual Abuse: a Critique of Organizational Behaviour and Management Policies (1989-2020)*, *Journal of Sexual Aggression*, DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2021.2018513).

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: Witnesses stand out among contemporary Christians for how seriously they believe God takes the threat of occult forces, witchcraft, and sorcery.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: Though Witnesses don't observe many rituals, that does not mean they believe God is neutral on the subject of ritual. To Jehovah's Witnesses, what God cares about is generally that his people NOT observe rituals like holidays. Witnesses believe that most rituals that have pagan roots, idolatrous leanings, or reflect a non-biblical Christianity, and for them to partake in any way would be an affront to God.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: See above.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: God is immensely concerned with saving nonbelievers, and has entrusted this mission to the Witnesses.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: God cares immensely about poverty and injustice. But because he has promised to end all injustice soon with the imminent coming of his millennial kingdom, Jehovah's Witnesses generally see no sense in invest time and energy in addressing economic injustice in our current world.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: Witnesses see good personal hygiene as being related to spiritual health (<https://www.jw.org/en/library/magazines/g201411/live-clean-life/>).

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: God, Jesus, and his angels all care about one another.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: Witnesses believe that most human suffering (illness, hunger, loss) is a natural result of the fallen, sinful state of the individual or of the world they live in, not a punishment from God. The only punishment from God comes in the form of eternal death.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: When God rebuilds his perfect kingdom, only people who mirror his goodness and truth can live there. But because he designed humans with free will to choose whether or not to follow him, this means that those who have chosen to walk away from God must die.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Although witnesses stand out among Christians for their rejection of hell and of the idea of any kind of torment in the afterlife, they are very focused on the idea that all non-believers will die permanent deaths.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: God's punishment for the wicked is eternal death, with the alternative being eternal life in his new kingdom.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– No

Notes: Jehovah's Witnesses are adamant that God does not cause suffering, and does not punish humans throughout their lifetimes. Suffering may happen as a result of our choice to sin, or as a result of the sin of others. See <https://www.jw.org/en/bible-teachings/questions/why-did-the-holocaust-happen/> for a discussion of questions about whether God caused the Holocaust for an example of this reasoning.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: Although all rewards for faithful believers originate with Jehovah, they may be realized through actions taken by Jesus and his angels.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus and angels will be key to carrying out God's plan to reward the righteous.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

Notes: Although God is understood to answer prayers, and although believers expect to live healthier and happier lives by following his commandments, they also understand that as humans they are subject to suffering. As a Witness reported to me during my research, they also anticipate that this suffering will grow more and more difficult as Armageddon approaches.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Most believers will be rewarded for their faithfulness by being resurrected to live eternally on God's new earth, an earth free of suffering and sin. An elite few will be rewarded by being made co-rulers with Jesus in heaven.

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The possibility of eternal life in a perfect earth is arguably the main focal point of Jehovah's Witnesses' faith. Certainly, it is what they stress to potential converts today, as evidenced by things like their online Interactive Bible Course titled "Enjoy Life Forever!" It has also been historically stressed through, for example, leader Joseph Rutherford's slogan, "Millions now living will never die!"

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

Notes: Witnesses emphasize the happiness of eternal community with loved ones.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– Yes

Notes: Although most believers will be resurrected to the earth, it will be to a superior version of the earth. Those few resurrected to be co-rulers alongside Jesus will live in a new heaven, a superior realm to earth.

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

Notes: Witnesses believe that God blesses his followers in this lifetime for their faithfulness, but often in subtle ways. Witnesses trust that even when it does not seem like they are being rewarded, they may be being blessed in ways they cannot comprehend.

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

Notes: One way Witnesses see God's blessings in their lives is through familial harmony and through inner peace.

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
– No

Notes: Although Witnesses believe that following Biblical commandments can help people to stay healthy (<https://www.jw.org/en/library/magazines/awake-no3-2019-nov-dec/physical-health/>), they see sickness and death as an unavoidable result of the fallen state of the world, and believe that most of God's physical healing will come at Armageddon rather than in their daily lives.

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
– No

↳ Other [specify]
– Yes

Notes: Even as Witnesses are in the midst of death and suffering, they may see the fact that they are able to stand strong in their faith and continue to spread God's truth as evidence of God's blessing. For an example of this logic, see: <https://www.jw.org/en/library/magazines/w20000301/Their-Faith-Was-Rewarded/>.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

↳ Alive, identified:

– No

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: Generations of Witnesses dating back to the group's inception have anticipated the return of Christ to earth - along with all of the cosmic changes that this arrival will trigger - within their lifetimes. J.F. Rutherford's 1918 slogan for the group, "Millions now living will never die!," showcases this fervent belief. The group now refrains from setting specific dates, but sees evidence that the end is near in global catastrophes from pandemics to climate change to war (<https://www.jw.org/en/library/magazines/watchtower-no2-2021-may-jun/what-jesus-said-about-the-end/>).

↳ Coming on specified date:

– No

Notes: The Jehovah's Witnesses embraced predictions of Christ's return in 1874, 1914, 1918, 1925, and 1975, and faced disappointment at each apparently failed prophecy (Holden, 1). Today, they argue that the exact date and time of Christ's coming is known only by Jehovah.

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Coming has already passed:

– No

Notes: Witnesses believe that Jesus has not yet arrived on earth for the Battle of Armageddon. However, they argue that Jesus assumed the throne of heaven and expelled Satan in 1914. We are therefore in a time of messianic transition (what the Witnesses call the "Last Days") in which Satan is wreaking havoc on the earth and Jesus is preparing to conquer him once and for all. This was explained to me in a one-on-one Bible Study with a Jehovah's Witness.

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– No

Notes: Witnesses are emphatic that Jesus is the only messiah who can accomplish Jehovah's divine plan to remake the earth.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– Yes

Notes: The Jehovah's Witnesses abstain from all earthly political participation, but frame Jesus and the new kingdom he will establish on earth in explicitly political terms. Jesus will rule over the earth as a king, and an elite group of believers will rule with him as viceregents. When I asked a Jehovah's Witness whether a non-Witness could ever be granted a place in this new kingdom, she responded by comparing Christ's kingdom to a nation-state: "Did you ever know a country where you could break all of the laws and still be allowed to live there?"

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– No

Notes: Although Witnesses believe that Jesus will restore right religious practice, they don't describe his role as being one of a priest.

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: To purify the earth of sin and death

Notes: Witnesses believe that Jesus's return will tie up the narrative arc of sin and death that was set in motion when Adam first disobeyed God in the Garden of Eden. Through his sin, Adam introduced death into the world. (As was stressed to me in a Bible study with a Jehovah's Witness, although Eve also sinned, it was Adam's sin that mattered on a cosmological level.) By leading the Battle of Armageddon and scourging the earth of wickedness, Jesus will purify what Adam's first sin infected. Only then can the righteous live eternally on an Edenic Earth, which is what God always wanted for humankind.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Some of these norms have to do with ethical behavior, such as lying, cheating, sexual immorality, greed, etc. Others have to do with maintaining what Witnesses view as a Godly social structure or hierarchy. They believe children should respect and honor their parents, and also advocate for a firmly patriarchal social structure in which men are the heads of households and church leaders.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present (but not emphasized)

Notes: This distinction between conventional social norms and moral social norms is most significantly elaborated during discussions of how Jehovah's Witnesses around the world ought to fit into their home cultures. For example, a 1985 article in the Watch Tower's magazine, "Awake!" describes a Nigerian Witness feeling dissolving his plural marriage upon realizing it was immoral, though traditional in his region (<https://wol.jw.org/en/wol/d/r1/lp-e/101985163?q=plural+marriage&p=doc>). But the Jehovah's Witness' website also contains examples like an article on burial that actively affirms various cultural forms of burial as all equally moral (<https://www.jw.org/en/bible-teachings/questions/bible-about-cremation/>).

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: Moral norms are defined by the commandments of Jehovah, as laid out in the Bible and interpreted by the Watch Tower Society.

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals within contemporary world

Notes: Witnesses believe that Jesus' arrival changed certain moral laws, meaning that some behavior that was permissible in the Old Testament may now be classed as sinful. (For example, God allowed polygamy during the time of the ancient Israelites. But with the coming of Jesus, God "restored" the moral standard of monogamy that he had originally intended for humankind before the fall. <https://wol.jw.org/en/wol/d/r1/lp-e/101991330?q=polygamy&p=doc>) But in any given time period, God has the same moral laws for all humankind.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

Notes: Jehovah's Witnesses prohibit sex and sexual activity outside of the bounds of monogamous, heterosexual marriage. Adultery is the only reason for religiously permissible divorce (and subsequent remarriage).

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: Although the exact lines of where sexual activity becomes illicit in dating relationships has shifted over time and may vary based on social mores place-to-place, Jehovah's Witnesses generally caution against romantic touching and kissing outside of the bounds of marriage (<https://wol.jw.org/en/wol/d/r1/lp-e/101993766>). Many Jehovah's Witness texts on sex refer to Colossians 3:5's instructions that Christians should "deaden their bodily members." Anything that would incite sexual feelings outside of monogamous, heterosexual marriage (including pornography, sexting, and masturbation) is regarded as sinful. For an example of this logic, see <https://www.jw.org/en/bible-teachings/questions/what-does-the-bible-say-about-pornography/>. Homosexual sexual activity is also strictly prohibited and considered a perversion.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: As with males, females are forbidden to engage in any sexual activity outside the

bounds of heterosexual, monogamous marriage.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: Although Witnesses may choose to fast, they are urged not to do it out of a sense of obligation. Official church texts state that what pleases God is not the act of fasting but the attitude of humility which underpins it. (<https://wol.jw.org/en/wol/d/r1/lp-e/2009253>)

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: The only food taboo for Jehovah's Witnesses concerns blood; Witnesses cannot eat meat that has not been fully drained of its blood, and cannot eat foods like blood pudding or sausage.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: Being a Witness requires no literal sacrifice, but it does require the sacrifice of severed relationships with any disfellowshipped or apostate Witnesses, including friends, family members, and even spouses.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: As with adult relationships, Witnesses may be asked to sacrifice relationships with their own children if they are disfellowshipped or commit apostasy. Though this is not framed as sacrificial in official literature, it may be experienced or framed as sacrificial to members; as an example, in an

interview with the podcast "Was I in a Cult?" ex-Witness Daniel O'Brien quotes a fellow Witness as saying, "If I have to step over my daughter's dead body at Armageddon to get into paradise, I will step ON her." (<https://www.podchaser.com/podcasts/was-i-in-a-cult-1979023/episodes/jehovahs-witnesses-shut-up-and-99150876>, 36:45)

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

↳ To other in-group members:

– Yes

Notes: Jehovah's Witnesses do not mandate tithing, and stand out among Christian groups for their refusal to take donations during services or "pass around the hat." However, though privacy around donations is guarded, it is expected that all members will contribute to the Watchtower Society and its worldwide missions.

↳ To out-groups:

– Yes

Notes: The Watch Tower Society uses donated money to fund disaster relief (as detailed here: <https://www.jw.org/en/jehovahs-witnesses/activities/help-community/disaster-relief/>). However, Witnesses have a more complicated relationship to charity than many other Christian groups, though; their belief that Armageddon is imminent creates a relative disinterest in engaging in long term projects aimed at structural change. They also firmly believe that while money can help to alleviate temporary suffering, the only way to permanently help people is to give them the gift of God's truth (<https://www.jw.org/en/library/magazines/w20030601/Giving-That-Pleases-God/>).

↳ Destroyed:

– No

↳ Other:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: The sacrifice of time is perhaps the most important marker of being a Jehovah's Witness: time to attend regular meetings, held at least twice weekly at Kingdom Halls; often, time to attend routine prayer and ministry meetings, as well as any congregation-level committee meetings; and time to volunteer to proselytize door to door or in booths set up on the street. Witnesses are required to turn in

timecards reporting how much time they've spent each month proselytizing.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Yes

Notes: Although specific risks vary based on time and place, the notion that Jehovah's Witnesses should choose bodily harm over compromising their faith is a constant. For example, in countries like Russia, Jehovah's Witnesses have been imprisoned and tortured (<https://religiondispatches.org/where-is-american-christian-outrage-on-russias-treatment-of-jehovahs-witnesses/>). In an extreme example, in Nazi Germany, thousands of Jehovah's Witnesses were imprisoned and killed for their refusal to join the military or to disavow their faith. An additional risk stands out today: Jehovah's Witnesses have a prohibition against receiving blood transfusions. This prohibition is based on several Biblical verses (e.g. Genesis 9:4, Leviticus 17:14; Acts 15:20) that are interpreted by most other Jewish and Christian groups as simply forbidding the ingestion of blood as food. This prohibition has led to a number of legal clashes around the world over the disputed rights of a Jehovah's Witness parent to withhold blood transfusions from their child, or for a Jehovah's Witness who is a minor to refuse blood transfusions during a life-threatening medical crisis.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: Witnesses have developed an ethical system through biblical exegesis. They hold firm beliefs in codes of personal ethical conduct around issues such as lying, stealing, adultery, and even abortion. However, unlike many Christian groups, they draw a hard line around certain politically charged issues (like the death penalty) and refrain from making any ethical judgement on them because they believe that Witnesses are called by God to hold back from any and all political involvement.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Notes: Jehovah's Witnesses generally discourage members from forming strong bonds with anyone outside of the group. As sociologist Andrew Holden describes in the chapter "Inside, Outside" in his book "Jehovah's Witnesses: Portrait of a Contemporary Religious Movement," a concern that contact with outsiders will expose Witnesses to immoral situations, unnecessary temptations, or sinful behavior (e.g. swearing, sexual promiscuity, excessive drinking) leads many to avoid forming or investing in relationships outside of the religion.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 4

Notes: Jehovah's Witnesses participate in family-level or private rituals several times a day. They typically pray before meals, and have set times to read Bible verses as a family or to hold family Bible studies.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: Large scale rituals for Jehovah's Witnesses include baptism (which is performed as a ritual entry into the religion organization), marriage, an annual congregational celebration called the "Memorial of Jesus' Death," and weekly meetings. For a video of a Jehovah's Witness wedding in the American south, see <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=q6qYAE-giDo>.

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 25

Notes: Rituals typically take place on a congregational level. Congregations typically have about 100 members. However, within each congregation there are also smaller groups of about 20 that meet for home bible studies (Holden, 66).

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 48

Notes: Three times a week, Witnesses are committed to a group religious meeting - two at the Kingdom Hall, and one at a member's home. Additionally, many meet for outreach ministry work or for work as elders.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The Watchtower Society carefully details correct interpretation of the Bible, with extensive publications outlining everything from Biblical sexual ethics to Biblical hair care. Bible Studies provide an opportunity for Jehovah's Witnesses to enforce these shared interpretive principles.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Elders exert a high degree of control over congregants' behavior, and Witnesses...

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: This is somewhat true - congregations may meet on different days of the week from

one another, but within individual congregations home prayer meetings will be held simultaneously at a number of houses (Holden, 66).

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– No

Notes: Jehovah's Witnesses are accepting of male circumcision but don't demand it.

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

Notes: The taboo on eating blood or bloody meat is only activated as a social marker in cultures where blood-centered food (e.g. blood sausage) is popular or culturally important.

↳ Hair:

– Yes

Notes: Jehovah's Witness men typically have short hair. Ex-Jehovah's Witness Daniel O'Brien has describe this in interviews.

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Notes: Modest, neat dress is expected of Jehovah's Witnesses.

↳ Ornaments:

– No

Notes: Jehovah's Witnesses stand out among Christians for their rejection of the symbol of the cross, and therefore for their rejection of religious jewelry that features it. They believe that Jesus died on a stake rather than a cross (<https://www.jw.org/en/library/magazines/awake-no2-2017-april/the-cross-is-it-biblical/>), and also find the use of the cross as a symbol to be idolatrous.

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– No

↳ Other:

– Yes [specify]: Not celebrating holidays or participating in political displays.

Notes: The ways in which Jehovah's Witnesses most often stick out from the crowd, or stand out in institutions like schools, is through their refusal to celebrate holidays (or to observe them in any way, such as by doing holiday-themed crafts at school) and their refusal to participate in any political or patriotic rituals (e.g. reciting the pledge of allegiance, singing the national anthem at a sports game, etc.). For a brief description of a Jehovah's Witness child's experience of being marked by this kind of difference, see <https://medium.com/fearless-she-wrote/religious-trauma-is-real-and-more-survivors-need-to-speak-up-about-it-39429c677756>.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

Notes: Jehovah's Witnesses refer to one another as "Brother" and "Sister."

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Jehovah's Witnesses are found in almost every nation worldwide.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Famine relief can be available from a state source or from non-profits and private organizations.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Poverty relief may come from various states or from private organizations.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: Jehovah's Witnesses believe that children are responsible for caring for aging parents (<https://www.jw.org/en/bible-teachings/questions/elderly-caregiver-help/>).

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: It may be available through specific states or through private organizations.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Jehovah's Witnesses do not offer schooling on secular subjects, but they require members of all ages to engage in study of the Bible, and offer Bible Study courses online and through their congregations.

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: Extra-religious education varies place to place, but is typically offered by the state and typically (though not always) open to both men and women. Jehovah's Witnesses are discouraged from pursuing higher education (e.g. college and graduate degrees), because higher degrees are considered a distraction from the truth to be found in God's word - and because of their belief that an imminent Armageddon will soon render such things as degrees utterly irrelevant.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: Each congregation is led by a group of elders, all of whom are adult men. These elders fit into a hierarchical system of overseers and directors, all overseen by a New York-based "Governing Body" that sets doctrine and makes all organizational decisions (Harlan, 30).

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Jehovah's Witnesses formally eschew politics. This means they do not vote, do not run for political office, and do not engage in political debates. However, despite this avowed neutrality on all political matters, they still have to interact with political/state bureaucracies routinely.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: This varies place to place, but many Witnesses are hooked into city or state-run water systems.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: This varies place to place, but most Witnesses live in regions where states provide for transportation infrastructure and modes of public transportation.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: Jehovah's Witnesses stand out for their rejection of tithing. They believe it to be a part of Mosaic law that was rendered irrelevant by Jesus.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Witnesses are subject to taxation by government bodies.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Witnesses interact with state-run police forces worldwide.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Notes: Witnesses have "judicial committees" made up of Church Elders who handle congregants' cases of immorality. This can include non-legal issues like adultery, but have also historically been used to privately handle legal issues such as child abuse. For an example of one case where a report of child abuse was handled internally by the judicial committee, see <https://www.shawlocal.com/northwest-herald/news/crime-and-courts/2022/03/03/trial-for-jehovahs-witnesses-elders-underway-without-decision-from-judge-on-what-hell-consider-in-evidence/>.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Witnesses interact with state judicial systems in their home countries.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Notes: Exile from a geographic territory cannot be enforced, but exile from the Kingdom Hall can be.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Notes: The main method by which Jehovah's Witnesses can be internally punished is through being shunned, or "disfellowshipped." When someone is "disfellowshipped," they can no longer attend meetings, and all Jehovah's Witnesses are forbidden contact with them. This includes close friends and family. Illicit contact with a disfellowshipped individual is itself grounds for disfellowshipping.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: States that have punished Jehovah's Witnesses for practicing their faith have generally done so based on one of two rationales: either because Jehovah's Witnesses have been officially classed as an extremist group (as in Russia today), or because by opting out of political participation they either broke a law or disrupted patriotic norms (as in the United States, Turkmenistan, Singapore, and Malawi).

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: This varies place to place, but in states like the U.S., China, Russia, and Saudi Arabia Witnesses are subject to laws that include the possibility of execution.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Notes: In hostile states, Witnesses have been tortured by police throughout history and into the present day. This has happened most recently and egregiously in Russia (<https://abcnews.go.com/International/russias-mysterious-campaign-jehovahs-witnesses/story?id=78629389>).

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: Though rare, in states that have persecuted Jehovah's Witnesses, seizure of property has been a key form of punishment and repression. Again, Russia offers the most recent example (<https://www.wsj.com/articles/russia-seizes-property-from-jehovahs-witnesses-after-banning-group-11551885978>).

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: Although the Witnesses have judicial committees, they assess sin and mete out punishment in a non-formalized way.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Members are subject to the laws of their home country.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by

institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Jehovah's Witnesses have historically refused to serve in the military during times of peace or war, citing multiple Old Testament and New Testament verses about God's true followers choosing peace over the sword. However, they also don't actively protest against war. In nations without religious exemptions from military service, this has led to large numbers of Jehovah's Witnesses being jailed for refusing to serve. (<https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-54694964>)

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Jehovah's Witnesses are protected by (and subject to) state militaries.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: Jehovah's Witnesses have devoted enormous time and resources to translating the Bible along with other Jehovah's Witnesses printed materials into many languages, with the goal of making the Bible accessible to all humankind.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Jehovah's Witnesses generally speak the language of their home country or ethnic community.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In any other institutions that Jehovah's Witnesses interface with - secular schools, secular courts, etc. - in countries around the world, they will be using a non-religion-specific language.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: Witnesses mostly rely on the calendars of their home nation-states. Today, this generally means the Gregorian calendar. However, Jehovah's witnesses also mark the date of Jesus' last supper in accordance with the Jewish lunar calendar. The calendar has also been a source of great concern for Jehovah's Witnesses during various attempts to predict a date for Armageddon (which Witnesses have pegged at various times as 1874, 1914, 1918, 1925, and 1975).

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Jehovah's Witnesses use the same calendars as used by others in their home countries - usually, today, Gregorian calendars. However, there are two key exceptions to the norm in how most Jehovah's Witnesses conceptualize time. First, most Jehovah's Witnesses do not celebrate holidays (either religious or secular). Holidays can be rejected for a litany of reasons (e.g. for glorifying a specific human, for glorifying a nation, for encouraging immoral behavior, for having a history in the occult, for glorifying false gods, etc), and while there is no absolute ban on celebrating holidays, most Jehovah's Witnesses err on the side of observing no holidays. Second, Jehovah's Witnesses believe that we are in the end of days...

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

–Other [specify in comments]

Notes: There are various government aid programs and nonprofit food distribution that Witnesses may take part in in their home countries.